

Supplementary table 2. Statistical analysis of multiplex cytokine measurement in plasma.

	IL1a	IL1b	IL2	IL3	IL4	IL5	IL6	IL10	IL12 (p40)	IL12 (p70)	IL13	IL17a	Eotaxin	G-CSF	GM-CSF	IFNg	KC	MCP-1	MIP-1a	MIP-1b	RANTES	TNFa	
6H	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	
1D	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
3D	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
7D	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
14D	ns	*	ns	*	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	*	ns	ns	*	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

Student *t*-test followed by Holm-Sidak's post-hoc test to correct for multiple comparisons between sham operated mice and HI mice at each time point. n= 5 for sham group and n= 8 for HI groups. ns: not significant, *p < 0.05